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SOURDOUGH TECHNOLOGY AS A STRATEGY TO ENHANCE THE APPEARANCE, TEXTURE, AND SENSORY ATTRIBUTES OF WHEAT BREAD CONTAINING NON-GERMINATED AND GERMINATED ALFALFA SEED

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Bringing diversity in protein consumption represents a global challenge to combat public health, climate, and nature-related risks and achieve long-term food security. Legumes are a valuable source of proteins, however relatively long preparation time, digestive discomfort occurrence, presence of antinutrients, and their beany or bitter flavour limit their incorporation into widely consumed staple food such as bread. To counteract the mentioned drawbacks for legume flour inclusion into bread formulations, sourdough fermentation and germination arise as re-emerging trends in healthy food production. These natural, traditional, low-cost and green processes could be a valuable ally in enhancing and tailoring the texture, flavour, nutritional value, and shelf life of legume-containing bread. Among legumes, alfalfa (*Medicago sativa* L.) seed potential for inclusion in bread formulations is scarcely investigated. Therefore, this study aimed to evaluate the effects of sourdough fermentation on specific volume, crust and crumb colour, crumb texture and sensory acceptability of wheat bread containing 5 and 10% convective dried non-germinated (ASF) and germinated alfalfa seed flour (GASF). Sourdough fermentation increased bread specific volume (from 2.63 to 3.62 cm³/g) in samples with 5% ASF and GASF. However, a slight volume-depressing effect compared to control sourdough bread was observed in samples containing 10% ASF and GASF. Greater specific volumes of sourdough bread samples containing alfalfa flour were followed by lower crumb hardness (reduced from 3.82 to 1.68 N), especially pronounced in samples with 5% ASF and GASF. Darker crust and crumb colour with a prominent visual difference ($\Delta E > 2.3$) was obtained in bread samples containing ASF and GASF compared to control sourdough bread. Sourdough bread samples containing ASF and GASF were rated as more acceptable compared to control sourdough bread and standard wheat bread (without sourdough) according to a 5-point hedonic scale. Sensory acceptability was the highest for sourdough bread containing 5% ASF (4.46 points), followed by samples with 5 and 10% GASF (4.37 points), and 10% ASF (4.17 points). The reported results showed that sourdough fermentation combined with alfalfa seed flour addition is a winning strategy to enhance specific volume, colour, crumb softness and sensory acceptability of legume-containing bread.

Keywords: legumes, germination, colour, crumb texture, sensory evaluation

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